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The Voice of a Teacher: From a Teacher's Point of View

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Let me ask you something, why are teachers always at fault when a student performs poorly or when a student lacks proper behavior? Why do people blame teachers for everything? If a child doesn't know how to read, the teacher is accountable for it. If a learner fails his or her subjects, it's on the teacher again. Teachers may have shortcomings, flaws, and weaknesses, and sometimes encounter many challenges that may affect their productivity and well-being but that doesn't mean they are not doing their jobs as teachers. Teachers work tirelessly to inculcate, guide, and support their learners to be the best of their abilities.

Like anyone else, teachers have limitations and may face obstacles that affect their capability to fulfill all areas of their roles perfectly. But these things are oftentimes overlooked. However, these limitations and problems do not negate their valuable contributions as teachers to learners.

Why do learners fail? Why do learners misconduct? Why some learners doesn't know how to read? Why some learners doesn't know how to write a sentence? Attributing all these areas and instances of misconduct and poor behavior solely to teachers ignores the idea that educating a child is the responsibility of all; It is in fact the role of teachers, parents, students themselves, and the government. It is somehow unfair, inaccurate, and painful that teachers always take the blame. Blaming teachers without addressing properly these fundamental issues will only perpetuate a chain of misunderstanding, confusion, chaos, and ineffective solutions.

To somehow address these underlying issues, parents should also be aware of their roles. Parents should know that their guidance, support, and positive parental involvement are crucial factors in their child's well-being and academic success. Take note that what a child sees at home, will surely apply in the real world. A child is like a sponge, he or she is absorbing everything around them, especially in their homes where they spend and interact most of their time. We all know that the home environment is the foundation of a child's learning. Therefore, adults inside the home must create a nurturing environment and show positive behavior.

Every parent should know this perspective, if a child grows up in a home filled with respect, care, love, support, and encouragement, they for sure carry those qualities into their own lives. On the contrary, if they observe negativity, unhealthy habits, quarrels, or conflicts, they may replicate and imitate those patterns as well. Therefore,

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collaboration between parents and teachers is very important for the success and overall well-being of learners. They cater both the academic and personal needs of learners.

On the other hand, learners themselves play crucial roles in their academic achievement and development. They should take responsibility for their progress, by knowing how to manage their time effectively, set objectives wisely, and being proactive, and motivated. Moreover, participating in class lectures, engaging in learning activities, being present in class, and doing assignments and projects are all important in the academic achievement of learners. Learners should also know how to self-reflect so that they can identify areas for improvement and find ways to address them. But it is a sad reality that there are learners today who don't care at all if they are learning or not. We have learners who are lax and negligent towards studying. It's true that in some cases, students appear to be unmotivated or disengaged maybe because of several factors such as constant access to social media and mobile games.

Therefore, to address these challenges it requires a multifaceted approach among teachers, parents, policymakers, and the community. Blaming teachers is not the solution to addressing challenges to education, instead let us all provide our learners a support system that promotes positivity, motivation, and engagement. Let us be the reason that all learners succeed in their endeavors. Let us hope that our learners are still the hope of the nation.

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